

Autonomous EV's in India- Future of Auto Sector

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Introduction

Innovation- a process of creating new ideas, Workflow or Methods and translating or transforming these ideas into products or services. The successful implementation of innovative ideas in business is crucial for successful sustainability of organization. Bringing New Ideas in the Market increases the profitability and efficiency of the Business.

Innovation is a creative Process and it can be from either

1. Inside the Organization (Employees, Managers, or from internal R&D).
2. It can be form Outside the Organization (Suppliers, Media Reports, and Market Research)

Success of the Organization comes from implementing the selective innovative ideas in the Business. Electric Vehicles are the main focus of Indian Government from the year 2025. It also started announcing various schemes to boost the usage of EV's in India other than Gasoline Cars. EV's has already in use in other countries like UK, USA and China Etc. Till date, EV's has its own advantage and disadvantage in other markets. Now, India is focusing to control the import of crude oil as it is trying to shift to EV's for which it has to overcome many barriers on the way. Autonomous EV Cars are future of World's Auto Market. Tesla, Uber, Google's Waymo are working on Autonomous cars. Google is hoping to introduce 100 Prototype subimpact Autonomous cars in a year. Autonomous cars works on Sensors and would focus on providing more comfort to Human. Introducing Self-Driven cars in the market is more complicated as it deals with public roads which if it goes wrong would cost human life. Considering slowdown in Automobile sector, itis becoming mandate for Automobile companies to come with Innovative Ideas.

Indian Auto Sector

India is the fourth largest producer of passenger cars in the world. The Two wheeler segment too dominates the market in terms of volume, thanks to growing middle class and young population. India is also strong in exporting the Automobiles to other countries, in the year 2014 it has exported around 14.5 Billion\$ Worth Units. Premium Motorbike sales in India have crossed 1 million units in the year 2018. Chennai is home for around 35% to 40% of India's total automobile Industry. After the Good run in April-June 2018, rising Crude oil prices affected the demands of Auto sector as India uses majority of variants as Petrol/ Diesel. Rural Demand which was growing at a higher rate earlier too slowed down. Researchers predict that the slowdown in the sector may be due to 1. Crude oil prices 2. GST 3. Commercial vehicles sales declined as Government gave to permission to carry high loads.

Electric Vehicles (EV)

Indian auto sector is witnessing a change as many Manufacturers and government is shifting the focus towards EV. Battery Electric Vehicles use electricity to function. It can be recharged again using grid electricity from a wall socket or Wall unit. Analysts say that EV vehicles emit less pollution than gasoline powered vehicles. As an initiative, Union Heavy Industries Ministry of India sanctioned 525 electric buses for Tamil Nadu. Additionally Government has announced Rs 1.5 Lakh income tax exemption for buying electric vehicles.

Hyundai, Country's second largest vehicle manufacturer has introduced electric sport vehicle on 9th July named Hyundai KONA Electric. It can cover till 450 Km and costs around 25.30 Lakh rupees. As the demand is expected to rise, EV Market might grow to about 300 Billion \$ by 2030. Government is aiming to make 7 Million vehicles by 2020.

Automated e-cars future of Indian Auto Industry

Autonomous Vehicles are believed to be one of the innovative and future of Auto Industry. Autonomous vehicles can guide themselves without human intervention to drive. It is also known as Self Driven car or Driverless Car. These cars work based on Radar sensors dotted around the car monitor to position the vehicles. Lidar(Camera)help to detect the edge of roads and it simply works like a Human eye. In 2015, UK Government announced new laws for testing Driverless cars and is targeting the investment of 20 Million Euros in to the technology. Car-to-infrastructure Communication is essential for enabling autonomous driving. Waymo, surpassed 9 million miles driven autonomously which started working on it form 2009.

According to SAE International Standards, Autonomous cars are rated from Level 0 to Level 5.

Level 0- No Automation

Level 1- Driver Assistance (Vehicle is controlled by the driver, but some driving assist features may be included)

Level 2- Partial Automation (Vehicle has combined Automated Functions, Like Acceleration and steering will be controlled automatically but the driver must monitor the environment)

Level 3- Conditional Automation (Vehicle can perform driving activities by itself but driver should always be ready to control the vehicle)

Level 4- High Automation (Vehicle is capable of driving on its own under certain conditions without human intervention. The driver may have the option to control the vehicle)

Level 5- Full Automation (Vehicle is capable of performing the driving activities on its own)

Tesla has launched thousands of Semi-Autonomous cars which is considered to be at Level 2 or Level 3. These cars allow you to take your hands off the wheel while your car can maintain the constant speed. The Autonomous car market has been valued at 5.68 Billion USD in 2018 and it

is expected to grow to 10 Billion USD by 2024. In India, Intel has started to gather data on traffic patterns, Infrastructure conditions and roadside behaviour.

EV Cars in India- Challenges

To bring the EV cars to usage in India has many challenges.

1. Cost

Cost of one of the main factor in market like India as majority of the Population falls under Mid Income Sector. Battery is one of the important component in EV Cars. Lithium batteries costs around 275\$/ KWh in India. GST also hovers around 28% for the batteries. Hyundai's recently launched EV car costs around 26 Lakhs which is on the higher side for the salaried group.

2. Time

Charging time for the car plays a Major role as it might create traffic in Charging stations. It is said that it normally takes 6 -8 hours to fully charge a EV car. This imposes a challenge in time management as each car can't wait for 6 hours to charge in EV charge stations.

3. Distance

It is claimed that a normal e-car can travel up to 150 KM to 200 KM after full Charge, Which is very low when compared to Gasoline cars where a car can full its tank within 5 minutes and can drive for more than 500 KM.

4. Infrastructure

As the waiting time for charging the Battery is high, It is important to set up more charging stations to facilitate recharging. Setting up Fast Charging stations is one of the important factor in EV segment. Currently in India there are more than 200 Charging stations which won't be enough to manage. Many also don't have proper power supply of 230V in their homes which also gets added to the difficulty.

5. Power

Another foremost thing to be considered is producing the Energy to light up these vehicles. Currently India produces it energy from various sources like Coal, Windmills, Hydro power, Nuclear Power Plant etc. As Coal is the main source, It requires more coals to produce power as it emits more Carbon while burned which adds to pollution.

Automated Cars- Challenges

Self-Driven Cars have more challenges to overcome. In 2018, a pedestrian Herzberg was killed by self-driven car of Uber where the car failed to stop.

Weather Conditions

Weather poses a major challenge. Unlike our eyes car sensors don't work well in fog or in rain. Self-Driven Cars should work well in all the climates.

Road Conditions

Not everywhere we find a clear and smooth road, we might see a bumpy road with more obstacles and also frequent pedestrians may cross over. In Mountains or even we have tunnels to crossover during highways where getting signal is a challenge.

Traffic Conditions

Autonomous Cars may have to drive with other Autonomous cars or even with humans who drive other cars. Humans deal with emotions and there is no guarantee that everyone follows traffic rules to precise. One can't wait for traffic to automatically clear as It may take more time which results in traffic deadlock.

Conclusion

To Conclude, In a Dynamic environment where we can see more innovative techniques emerging frequently, It is a must for an Organization to bring innovative ideas in the business to stay competitive. Implementation of EV might boost Indian Auto sector and it will benefit the society. EV cars also saves world's Non renewable energies like Gasoline and it also helps in reducing the pollution. But at the same time there are many challenges which are discussed above must be considered. Government should reduce taxes and increase the exemption in taxes for buying EV Cars or Bikes. It also should act quickly in keeping more EV Charging stations. Company's should also look into fast charging options to reduce the charging time which is considered as a major concern in using Electric Vehicles.

Automated Cars are the future for Automobile Sectors. This is an exciting Technology which has its own risk involved in it. While Autonomous cars creates more excitement, They still have a long way ahead before it is safe and regulated. While these cars will be more useful for transportation and increases human comfort, It works on Internet which is subjected to be hacked or jammed. Intel has launched its foot on collecting data for launch Self-Driven cars in India. It is to conclude that Self Driven cars combines the Auto Market with AI and brings in more advantages, At the same time Safety becomes priority where a middle aged driver scores more.

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